

doi:10.5281/zenodo.17896512

An Appraisal on the Application of Unstructured Supplementary Service Data Code in Online Banking Sector in Katsina Local Government Area, Katsina State

Surajo Abba Ahmed

**Department of General Studies
Sani Zangon Daura, School of Health Technology Daura, Katsina State
Katsina State College of Health Science and Technology, Nigeria
Author email : surajoabba2013@gmail.com**

ABSTRACT

Nigeria government is introducing cashless policy into the economy and that requires the use of transfer technology to buy and sell goods in the country. Nigerians have embraced the CBN's cashless policy, considering the way electronic transactions has grown in recent years. This research is aimed to assess the application of Unstructured Supplementary Service Data (USSD) in online banking transaction. Simple random sampling techniques was adopted to form the sampling, a sample size of 395 online bank customers were used for the study. A research questionnaire was design and administered to the customers to investigate problems encounter that restrict full utilization of USSD in online banking. Statistical mean was used to analyze the data obtained from the respondents. it was discovered that application of USSD CODE is simple and does not required the use of internet but many costumers just ignore the use due to many steps involved to execute single transaction and opt for the use of application. It was recommended among others: that network providers should increased their network bandwidths, all banks should provide a platform to reduce the number of steps taken to complete single financial transactions.

Keywords : USSD CODE, Banking, online, application, customer, transaction, KTLGA

INTRODUCTION

In Nigeria, Government is introducing cashless policies in all business sector of the economy, there is limited cash transaction. Here in Katsina many have resort to the use of online banking system, but internet banking have it own limitation to customers, many may not have Smartphone or there could be limited internet access or simply the customer may be out of data that would link him/her to internet. Therefore customer have no option rather than to use USSD banking system. in banking , USSD stand for Unstructured Supplementary Service Data, a session-based text messaging services that allows users to interact with banking services through a menu-based system on their mobile phones, without needing a Smartphone or internet connection.

USSD involved the practice of allowing users without data or internet connection and also Smartphone to make full utilization of mobile banking through the use of code. USSD based mobile banking can be used for checking account balance, fund transfers, and generating bank statements, recharging airtime etc. The main objective of the study is to assess the application of USSD code in online banking transaction in Katsina Local Government Area KTLGA.

- i. To determine technical knowledge (know-how) of using USSD Code by customers of a bank
- ii. To assess how easy the method of transaction is, using USSD code by customer of a bank
- iii. To determine acceptability of USSD code transaction to customers of a bank
- iv. To determine problems that hinder proper utilization of USSD code by customer of a bank.

Research Questions

- i. How knowledgeable is the customer of a bank with regards to the use of USSD Code to make financial transaction?
- ii. How easy does the customer of a bank make financial transaction using USSD Code?
- iii. How acceptable is USSD Code to customer of a bank over other ways of money transaction?
- iv. What are some of the problems that hinder full utilization of USSD Code during financial transaction?

LITERATURE REVIEW

How Ussd Code Works

USSD (Unstructured supplementary service data) allows mobile users to interact with a service provider’s network by dialing a short code (* code #) sending a request and receiving a response displayed on their phone screen, all without needing a data connection (Rosencrance, 2020).

USSD involves sending a request from a mobile phone user such as a request for a bank account balance, recharge card balance, once the user sends the request, the USSD gateway forwards it to the user’s USSD application, which responds to the request. The process is then repeated in reverse, the response is been display on the screen of the user’s mobile phone. The users send and receive data by dialing a specific short code (Rosencrance, 2020).

USSD runs on the network, not on user’s device. The application need not to be installed on user’s phone, this is an advantage for mobile phone with limited storage space. USSD are instantly available to every subscriber the moment they are deployed to a network (Rosencrance, 2020).

In Nigeria the value of USSD transfer payment has significantly increased. From January 2020, the volume of USSD transfer payment increased from roughly 30 Billion Naira to 551 Billion Naira (Sasu, 2022) .

Nigerian Communication Commission (NCC) on USSD

The Nigerian Communications Commission (NCC) is the regulatory body responsible for USSD codes in Nigeria, and it has implemented a unified USSD code framework for all mobile network operators. This means that while previously each network had its own unique USSD codes, they are now using a standardized set of codes across the board (Nwokoma, 2023).

Examples of New Codes: (Nwokoma, 2023)

- ✕☎ *312# - Data Plans
- ✕✕☎ *311# - Recharge
- ✕✕✕☎ *303# - Borrow Airtime
- ✕❖☎ *323# - Data Balance
- ❖☎ *310# - Account Balance
- ❖✕☎ *321# - Share Data
- ❖✕✕☎ *305# - VAS
- ❖✕✕✕☎ *996# - NIN

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research intended to obtain information from customers of bank randomly on the assessment of application of USSD Code in online banking sectors. The research targeted any bank customers that have mobile phone and were expose to the use of USSD code and its application in katsina local government area (KTLGA),katsina state . The sample size of the study was 399 customers as respondents to the study. A simple random sampling technique was adopted for the study in the selection of the sample.

A structured questionnaire was used as data gathering instrument. A-5 point likert scale of Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed(A),Undecided(U),Disagreed(D),and Strongly Disagreed(SD) with numerical values of 5,4,3,2,1 respectively was used. The instrument used was title “Questionnaire to CUSTOMERS on Assessment on the Application of USSD Code in Online Banking Sector (QCAAUSSDCOBS)”. The instruments consist of 23 item questions based on the research questions. The respondent’s responses in the questionnaire items were used to analyze the research questions. Two experts in the field of measurement and evaluation from Sani Zangon Daura School of Health Technology, Daura validated the instrument. Their observation and corrections were effected before it was administered to the respondents. The data collected which was used based on the research questions that guide the study was analyzed using statistical mean. An item with a calculated mean value of equal to or greater than 3.5 was accepted, while item with mean value of less than 3.5 was rejected.

RESULTS

Research Question 1. How knowledgeable are the customers of a bank with regards to the use of USSD Code to make financial transaction.

TABLE 1: Mean rating of respondents on the knowledge of customers of a bank with regards to the use of USSD Code to make financial transactions.

(N=395)

S/N	Test of Knowledge	Customer X ₁	Decision
1.	You know what is USSD code	4.35	ACCEPTED
2.	You are familiar with how to use USSD code	3.95	ACCEPTED
3.	You can make transaction without the use of internet	3.91	ACCEPTED
4.	USSD application requires advance qualification to make financial transaction in a bank	3.53	ACCEPTED
5.	Somebody with elementary /secondary school qualification can use USSD code to make financial transaction in a bank	4.09	ACCEPTED
6.	Person who did not attend school can still use USSD code to make financial transaction	4.09	ACCEPTED
Total Mean(X_T)		3.98	ACCEPTED

The results of the analysis in Table 1 indicate that the respondents accept all items from item 1 to 6. The grand mean indicated acceptance thus customers of bank have knowledge with regard to the use of USSD Code.

Research Question 2: *How easy does the customer of a bank make financial transaction using USSD Code?*

TABLE 2: Mean rating of respondents on how easy does the customers of bank make financial transaction using USSD Code (N=395).

S/N	items	Customer X_1	Decision
7.	USSD code is difficult to use	2.70	REJECTED
8.	Steps taken to make transaction using USSD code is difficult.	3.49	REJECTED
9.	USSD code is simple and easy to use	3.96	ACCEPTED
10.	Steps taken to make bank transaction using USSD code is simple and easy	3.89	ACCEPTED
11.	Steps taken to make financial transaction is clear	3.21	REJECTED
Total Mean(X_T)		3.45	ACCEPTED

The result of the analysis in table 2 indicated that the respondents rejected item 7 and 11, and accepted item 8,9,10. The grand mean is within acceptable range by approximation, thus indicated that, it is easy for customers to make financial transaction using USSD Code in Katsina Local government authority.

Research Question 3: *How acceptable is USSD Code to customer of a bank over other ways of money transaction?*

TABLE 3: Mean rating of acceptability of USSD Code to customer of a bank over other ways of money transaction (N=395)

S/N	items	Customer X_1	Decision
12.	USSD Code are better than software Application of a bank in making a financial Transaction.	4.26	ACCEPTED
13.	I have used USSD in making Financial transaction before and it works fine.	3.83	ACCEPTED
14.	I used USSD to make other transaction not only in bank like checking recharge card balance.	3.60	ACCEPTED
15.	USSD code works in the absence of internet well	3.78	ACCEPTED
16.	USSD code is cheap and affordable in making data transaction	3.63	ACCEPTED
Total Mean(X_T)		3.82	ACCEPTED

The result of the analysis in table 3 indicated that the respondents accepted all the items from 12 to 16. The grand mean is within acceptable range , thus indicated that , USSD Code is acceptable to customers of banks over other ways of making banking transactions in Katsina Local government authority .

Research Question 4: *What are some of the problems that hinder full utilization of USSD Code during financial transaction?*

Table 4: mean rating of problems that hinder full utilization of USSD Code during financial transactions in Katsina Local Government Area of Katsina (N=395).

S/N	items	Customer X_1	Decision
17.	There is sufficient time to complete transaction	2.78	REJECTED
18.	There are too many steps to perform before completing a transaction	3.10	REJECTED
19.	USSD is complex and difficult	4.01	ACCEPTED
20.	USSD requires to many task	4.03	ACCEPTED
21.	There is network problems or poor services before completing transaction	3.75	ACCEPTED
22.	There is network congestion when using USSD code..	3.35	REJECTED
Total Mean(X_T)		3.50	ACCEPTED

The result of the analysis in table 4 indicated that the respondents rejected item 17, 18, and 22 and accepted item 19, 20, and 21. the grand mean is within acceptable range , thus indicated that all the problem mention above affects customer of a bank using USSD CODE while making a financial transaction in Katsina Local Government Area of Katsina State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

From the outcome of the analysis carried out, the researcher was able to outline the following findings:

1. The results revealed that customer of a bank are very much familiar with the use of USSD CODE even without internet connections. The research also revealed that customers with basic/little or no education can still successfully operate USSD CODE to make financial transaction thus indicate that operating USSD CODE does not require advance knowledge to operate. This result is in agreement with the finding of (Avik Malik, 13 Nov, 2020) , sited that USSD CODE allow unbanked populace to access banking system without needing internet connectivity.
2. The result indicated that customers of a bank find it easy to make financial transaction using USSD CODE; furthermore the steps taken to complete a financial transaction using USSD CODE is simple and clear. This result is in agreement with the findings of (Ebole Alpha Friday, 6 June 2022) sited that adoption of mobile money can ease financial inclusion in Nigeria.
3. The results revealed that customer of a bank accepted USSD Code application in bank transaction as a better option over the use of application , because USSD Code work perfectly fine for the customers and also work in the absence of internet, the customers used it in other engagement different from banking transaction like checking recharge card available balanced e.t.c.

4. The study was able to identify some of the problems that hinder effective utilization of USSD Code in banking transaction. These constraints include insufficient time to complete financial transaction, application of USSD Code involves too many steps and task, sometimes customer of bank experienced network problem or poor services before completing financial transactions, and also customers experienced network congestion when using USSD CODE application in making financial transaction in Katsina Local Government Area of Katsina State. All these problems pose a barrier to effective utilization of USSD Code here in KTLGA.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made in this paper:

1. Network provider should increase their network bandwidth to reduce network congestion, traffic of packages.
2. The government through communication regulation commission (Nigeria Communication Commission NCC) should maintain a unique USSD CODE to all banks, these would greatly help customer retain the code and apply the code where necessary.
3. The banks and network providers should collaborate together and introduce a new system that would reduce steps taken to complete a financial transaction.
4. The banks and network providers should collaborate together and introduce a unique USSD Code that can be applicable to all banks irrespective of the bank a customer operates, just like how NCC harmonize USSD Code in network provider. (e.g. *310# stand for account balance check across all network).
5. The banks should introduce a new system that would reduce step taken for a customer to complete a single financial and also increase the time session for a transaction not to be MMI invalid.

CONCLUSION

The studies conclude that USSD CODE is a very important tool in making financial transaction. Application of USSD code has greatly reduced the burden experienced by customers of a bank while performing banking transaction since customers do not have to own a Smartphone or having an internet connection to carry out banking services. The research work was able to identify that application of USSD Code by customer of a bank do not require any advanced knowledge to carry out a financial transaction and also very simple to use. Similarly it was discovered that USSD CODE application is acceptable to customer of bank over other method of financial transaction despite many of its steps involve in making transaction. However the research conclude that poor network service, network congestion, and many task involves to complete a transaction are some of the major problems that hinder full utilization of USSD Code in performing financial transaction in banks.

REFERENCES

- Avik Malik, C. T. (13 Nov, 2020). USSD Digital Wallet. *2020 Intemountain Engineering, Technology and Computing (IETC) Conference*, 3.
- Ebole Alpha Friday, S. A. (6 June 2022). Power of USSD: A solution to African Financial Problems. *International Journal of computer science and mobile application*, 19.
- Hanouch, M. (17 Feb. 2015). *What is USSD & Why Does it Matter for Mobile Financial Services?* 1818 H Street, NW, MSN F3K-306, Washington, DC 20433: CGAP.
- Nwokoma, C. (2023, May 23). *Why the Nigerian Communications Commission is pushing for harmonised short codes*. Retrieved April 11, 2025, from Techpoint.Africa: <https://techpoint.africa/news/new-ussd-codes-for-network-providers-in-nigeria/>
- Rosencrance, L. (2020, March). *What is USSD (Unstructured Supplementary Service Data)?* Retrieved April 10, 2025, from Techtarget: <https://www.techtargget.com/searchnetworking/definition/USSD#>
- Sasu, D. D. (2022, December 12). *Value of unstructured supplementary service data (USSD) transfers in Nigeria from January to December 2020*. Retrieved April 11, 2025, from Statista: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1175329/monthly-value-of-ussd-transfer-payments-in-nigeria/>